

3,4,5-Trimethyl-1-thiocarbamylpyrazole as a Chelating Agent

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Metallic complexes of the tetra-substituted pyrazole, 3,4,5-trimethyl-1-thiocarbamyl pyrazole, with Cu(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Pd(II) and Co(III) have been isolated and characterized and their structures have been suggested from the study of elemental analysis, conductance, electronic spectral and magnetic moment data. A tetrahedral stereochemistry has been suggested for the Co(II) complex, while octahedral configurations have been suggested for Co(III), Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes. The Ni(II) and Pd(II) complexes have been assigned square-planar structures and the Cu(II) complex has a planar or a tetragonally distorted octahedral stereochemistry. It is also suggested that the 'thiol' form of the ligand takes part in the complex formation.

Organic heterocyclic compounds have long been known for their complex-forming ability with the transitional metal ions. Recently a number of communications have appeared on the metallic complexes of pyrazole and its substituted products.¹⁻¹¹ The present paper describes the complex-forming ability of a tetra-substituted pyrazole, *viz.*, 3,4,5-trimethyl-1-thiocarbamyl pyrazole (1a), which contains in its molecule the coordination functions of the tertiary nitrogen of the pyrazole ring and also the thiocarbamido group in positions suitable for chelate ring formation with the metal ions. A number of compounds of formula ML_n have been synthesised, where M stands for the metal ion and n the number of positive charge in it, and L represents the anion of the 'thiol' form (1b) of the ligand.

Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Co(III), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pd(II) complexes of the ligand have been isolated and characterised on the basis of elemental analyses, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility values as well as from visible spectral data.

Fig 1(a)

Fig 1(b)

Fig 2

Materials and Methods : 3,4,5-trimethyl 1-thiocarbamyl pyrazole was prepared by condensing 3-methyl acetyl-acetone and thiosemicarbazide according to the method given in literature¹². The crude product was recrystallised from ethanol. The substance is soluble in hot ethanol, acetone, chloroform and melts at 103°–104°.

The elemental analyses were done by conventional methods. Visible spectra were taken in chloroform solution in a "Spectromom-20" (Hungarian) spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured in a Gouy balance using $\text{HgCo}(\text{CNS})_4$ as the calibrant¹³. Electrolytic conductances of solutions were measured in a Philips PR 9500 type conductivity bridge. All the chemicals used were of chemically pure grade.

Preparation of the complexes :

Copper bis(3,4,5-trimethyl 1-thiocarbamyl pyrazole) : When a solution of the ligand (0.62 g., .004 mole) in ethanol (20 ml) was added to a solution of copper chloride dihydrate (.34 gm, .002 mole) also in ethanol (20 ml), a dark green solution resulted. Dropwise addition of dilute ammonia solution to the mixture with constant stirring produced a brownish red crystalline precipitate. This was filtered, washed with water and hot ethanol and dried in air. The substance is insoluble in water, acetone, benzene and ether but is slightly soluble in chloroform giving a reddish brown solution. It is freely soluble in pyridine producing a bluish green solution.

Nickel bis(3,4,5-trimethyl 1-thiocarbamyl pyrazole) : To a solution of nickel chloride hexahydrate (0.42 g. .002 mole) in ethanol (20 ml) a solution of the ligand (0.62 g, .004 mole) in ethanol (20 ml) was added, when a green solution was formed. This, on addition of ammonia, produced a voluminous red precipitate which was filtered, washed with water and hot ethanol and dried in air. The compound is soluble in chloroform, but insoluble in water and other common organic solvents.

Cobaltic tris(3,4,5-trimethyl 1-thiocarbamyl pyrazole) : A solution of the ligand (0.93 g, .006 mole) in ethanol (20 ml) was mixed with a solution of cobalt chloride hexahydrate (0.42 g, .002 mole) also in ethanol (20 ml). The mixture was heated on water bath with dropwise addition of ammonia with constant stirring. After sometime an orange-yellow precipitate began to settle down. This was collected on a filter, washed with water and hot ethanol and recrystallised from chloroform. The substance is insoluble in water and other common organic solvents.

Cobaltous bis(3,4,5-trimethyl 1-thiocarbamyl pyrazole) : When the above orange yellow cobaltic complexes were heated in an air oven at 150° for about an hour, it melted to a blue mass. The mass was cooled and extracted with ethanol. The ethanolic solution was evaporated to dryness and the residue was again extracted with ether and filtered. The ethereal solution was kept in a refrigerator overnight, when deep blue crystals were deposited. They were collected on a filter, washed with cold ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused CaCl_2 . The compound is insoluble in water but soluble in all common organic solvents.

Diammino-zinc bis(3,4,5-trimethyl 1-thiocarbamyl pyrazole) : An ethanolic solution (20 ml) of the ligand (0.62 g, .004 mole) was added to a solution of zinc acetate dihydrate (0.44 gm, .002 mole) in ethanol (20 ml). Dilute ammonia was then added dropwise to the

mixture when glistening white crystals were obtained. These were filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried in air. It is soluble in boiling ethanol but insoluble in acetone, chloroform and ether.

Diaquo zinc bis(3,4,5-trimethyl-1-thiocarbamyl pyrazole): This compound was obtained as a white precipitate by a method similar to that adopted for the diammine complex, but using 4*N* NaOH solution in place of dilute ammonia. The product was filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried in air. The substance is insoluble in water and acetone, sparingly soluble in ethanol but easily soluble in chloroform.

Diaquo cadmium bis(3,4,5-trimethyl 1-thiocarbamyl pyrazole): To a mixture of solutions of cadmium acetate (0.52 g, .002 mole) in ethanol (20 ml) and the ligand (0.62 g, .004 mole) also in ethanol (20 ml), was added dilute ammonia dropwise with constant stirring when a white precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried in air. The compound is insoluble in water, acetone and ether but soluble in hot ethanol and chloroform.

Palladium bis(3,4,5-trimethyl-1-thiocarbamyl pyrazole): To a solution of a palladium chloride (0.36 g.) in dilute HCl, an ethanol solution (20 ml) of the ligand (0.62 g, .004 mole) was added. Dilute ammonia was added to the mixture dropwise till a yellow precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried in air. The substance is insoluble in ethanol, slightly soluble in methanol but readily soluble in chloroform.

Analytical data

Compounds	% Metal		% Nitrogen		$\mu_{B_{eff}}$ at 30°
	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	
Cu(L) ₂	15.90	16.02	21.03	21.10	1.76
Co(L) ₃	10.45	10.54	22.39	22.45	Diamagnetic
Co(L) ₂	14.91	14.78	21.27	21.29	4.23
Ni(L) ₂	14.87	14.72	21.28	21.32	Diamagnetic
Zn(L) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	14.95	14.88	19.21	19.13	—
Zn(L) ₂ ·2NH ₃	15.02	15.55	25.72	25.80	—
Cd(L) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	23.53	23.62	17.65	17.72	—
Pd(L) ₂	23.98	24.04	19.03	19.12	Diamagnetic

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The conductance measurements of the solutions of the complexes in nitrobenzene show that they are all non-electrolytes.

Cobalt(III) complex: The octahedral stereochemistry, which is typical for a hexacoordinated Co(III) complex, has been suggested for the orange-yellow, diamagnetic Co(III) complexes under study. The visible spectrum of the solution of the complex shows two bands at 15870 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon = 125$) and 24096 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon = 1895$), corresponding to the transition

from the $^1A_{1g}$ ground state to upper singlet state $^1T_{1g}$ and $^1T_{2g}$ respectively. The higher value of molar extinction coefficient at the higher frequency region is probably due to the interaction of the ligand field band with the charge transfer one as suggested by earlier workers^{14,15}.

Cobalt(II) complexes : The thermal reduction of the above Co(III) complex to Co(II) complex $Co(II)L_2$ by heating around 150° is supposed to be effected by a mechanism similar to those given for the Cu(II) complexes of triethylamine and benzophenoneimine^{16,17}. Co(II) complex $Co(II)L_2$ is assigned a tetrahedral stereochemistry which is characteristic of Co(II) complex with such an intense blue color. This is further supported by the spectral and magnetic moment data. The observed magnetic moment 4.23 BM is well within the range expected for tetrahedral stereochemistry of the Co(II) ions¹⁸⁻²⁰. The compound shows an intense absorption at 16126 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 637$), which is due to the transition from 4A_2 ground state to $^4T_1(P)$ state.

Ni(II) complexes : The red coloured Ni(II) L_2 complex is diamagnetic and its solution spectrum shows an intense absorption band at 24400 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 1678$), which is typical for the square-planar Ni(II) complexes and is attributed to $^1A_{1g}$ to $^1A_{2g}$.²¹⁻²³ The high value of molar extinction coefficient is supposed to be due to the intermixing of the charge transfer band with the ligand field band in the visible region. A square-planar stereochemistry is therefore, proposed for the Ni(II) complex under investigation.

Copper(II) complexes : The magnetic moment 1.76 BM of the red copper complex is found to be considerably lower than that generally observed in the case of octahedral copper(II) complexes^{24,25}. The lower value of the magnetic moment in this case may be due to a square-planar or tetragonally distorted octahedral stereochemistry of the complex. In such arrangements, the separation between the ground $^2B_{1g}$ and the $^2T_{2g}$ levels increases resulting in the lowering of magnetic moment values. A tetrahedral stereochemistry is excluded as in such cases the magnetic moment value would have been still higher due to spin-orbit coupling^{24,25}.

The brownish red chloroform solution of the Cu(II) complex shows only a single absorption band at 18860 cm^{-1} together with an intense charge transfer band at 22200 cm^{-1} region. In the presence of a coordinating solvent like pyridine, the absorption peak shifts to lower frequency region (14000 cm^{-1}) suggesting a change in stereochemistry of the complex species in solution of the solvent. This may be due to the fact that in the solution of the coordinating solvent new complex species with coordinated solvent molecules are formed in solution²⁶⁻³¹. One interesting feature of the complex is its unusual red colour, whereas the tetra coordinated Cu(II) complexes have generally blue, green or violet colour. Yamada and Miki³¹ suggested two important factors which may be responsible for such coloration. These are : (i) the steric condition of the ligand and (ii) the π -bond formation between the donor atoms and cupric ions. In the present case, an overlap of the vacant low-lying 3d-orbital of the sulphur atoms and the filled orbitals of the Cu(II) ions is possible, resulting in a metal \rightarrow ligand back bonding (π -type) and thereby stabilizing the square planar configuration³². This along with the stereochemical arrangement of the ligand atoms around the central metal ion would explain the red-colour of the complex considering the magnetic

moment value, spectral data and the colour of the complex, a square planar stereochemistry appears to be more appropriate for the compound under study.

Pd(II) complexes : The yellow Pd(II) complex Pd(II)L₂ is diamagnetic and like all other Pd(II) complex it is assumed to have a square planar configuration.

Octahedral stereochemistries have been suggested for the diamagnetic Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes as is common for these ions.

It appears from the nature of the metallic complexes formed by the ligand that it behaves as a monoprotic bidentate one. The substituted pyrazole probably reacts with the metal ions in its 'thiol' form to give the non-electrolyte complexes (Fig. 2). The cadmium complex described above starts decomposition after a few days giving CdS. The silver(I) complex of the ligand, though formed as a crystalline white solid below 0°, could not be isolated in the pure state due to its decomposition to Ag₂S in contact with air at room-temperature. The formation of these metallic sulphides seems to suggest the metal sulfur bond in the complexes and support the structures of the complexes shown in Fig. 2.

REFERENCES

1. R. T. Pflaum and L. H. Dieter, *Proc. Iowa Acad. Sci.*, 1957, **64**, 233.
2. D. R. Crow, *J. Polarogr. Soc.*, 1965, **11**, 67.
3. C. W. Reiman and A. D. Mighell, *J. Phys. Chem.*, Ithaca, 1967, **71**, 2375.
4. N. A. Daugherty, and Swisher, J. H., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 1651.
5. H. Henning and U. Eckelmann, *Z. anorg. allg. chem.*, 1968, **363**, 127.
6. A. N. Nesmeyanov, M. I. Rubinkuja, N. S. Kochetkova, V N. Babin and G. B. Shulpin, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk. S.S.S.R.*, 1968, **181**, 1397.
7. S. N. Poddar, *Science & Culture*, 1969, **35**, 28.
8. S. N. Poddar, K. Dey and N. G. Podder, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 364.
9. D. Nicholls and B. A. Warburton, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 1041.
10. D. Nicholls and B. A. Warburton, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 3871.
11. M. J. Bagley, D. Nicholls and B. A. Warburton, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 2694.
12. F. L. Scott, D. G. Donovan, M. R. Kennedy and J. Reilly, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, **22**, 820.
13. B. N. Figgis and J. Lewis, *Modern Coordination Chemistry* (Interscience Publishers Inc., New York), 1960, 416.
14. S. Yamada, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1967, **2**, 83.
15. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson. *Advance inorganic chemistry* (Interscience Publishers Inc., New York), 1966, 875.
16. J. F. Weiss, G. Tollin and J. T. Yoke, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 1344.
17. A. Misono, T. Osa and S. Koda, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1968, **41**, 373.
18. B. N. Figgis and R. S. Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 338.
19. S. Yamada, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, **1**, 415.
20. J. R. Wasson, K. K. Ganguly and L. Theriot, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 2807.
21. W. Manch and W. C. Fernelius, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1961, **38**, 192.

22. H. B. Gray and C. J. Ballhausen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 260.
23. W. K. Musker and M. S. Hussain, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 528.
24. B. N. Figgis and C. M. Harris, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 855.
25. B. N. Figgis and J. Lewis. Progress in inorganic chemistry, vol. 6, edited by F. A. Cotton (Interscience Publishers Inc., New York), 1964, 37.
26. D. P. Graddon and E. C. Watton, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1961, **21**, 49.
27. H. M. N. H. Irving and N. S. Ali Niame, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 1671.
28. W. R. Walker and N. C. Li, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 2255.
29. W. R. May and M. M. Jones, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 507.
30. T. N. Water and D. Hall, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1200, 1203.
31. S. Yamada and S. Miki, *Bull. Chem. Soc.*, Japan, 1963, **36**, 680.
32. M. J. Campbell and R. Grzeskowiak, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 196(A), 396.
33. S. Ahrland, J. Chatt and N. R. Davis, *Quart. Rev. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **12**, 265.